

Combining ability analysis on restorability for cytoplasmic male sterility in hybrid rice

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Restorability, estimated as the mean spikelet fertility or seed set percentage in the F₁ generation, refers to the potential of a certain cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line to restore fertility in the hybrid derived from it. It is caused by nuclear gene(s) of the restorer (R) lines, and nuclear (N) and cytoplasmic (C) background of the CMS (A) line, as well as the interaction between the two. To understand the relative importance of each factor, three series of iso-nuclear lines with three types of CMS backgrounds (nine CMS lines) were developed. Then we produced 72 combinations according to North Carolina Design II (9 CMS lines, 8 restorers). In the summer of 1994, each combination was grown in two rows with 9 plants each at 33.3- × 20-cm spacing. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications in which the main factor was the restorers. Data on seed set percentage were collected from the center five plants of either row. Statistical analysis was based on the sin⁻¹√p transformation data.

General combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) values^a for restorability for CMS.

CMS line nuclear background	Restorers								GCA	SE
	6323	72922	Ce-64	Hui-403	HR195	Hui-552	CDR22	Minghui-63 (check)		
N-Qing	1.49*	-0.90	-1.02	-1.74**	-0.84	0.61	0.78	1.62*	1.80**	
N-17	-0.18	-0.56	0.11	-0.14	-0.33	1.38*	-0.61	0.34	-0.41	
N-Shan (check)	-1.30*	1.45*	0.91	1.88**	1.18	-1.98**	0.17	-1.96**	-1.39**	
GCA	-4.25**	1.44	0.03	2.00*	3.70**	-4.55**	2.08*	-0.46		0.232
SE									0.72	0.614

^a*, ** = significance at 0.05 and 0.01 level, respectively.

Variance analysis revealed that effects on restorability were significantly different among restorers, CMS line nuclear backgrounds, and N-R interactions, while not significantly different among the cytoplasmic background of CMS lines, C-R interactions, C-N interactions, and C-N-R interactions.

Subsequent analysis of combining ability showed that HR195 and N-Qing had the highest general combining ability (GCA) among restorers and N-Qing among nuclear background of CMS lines. Among the restorers, the GCA for restorability of CDR22, Hui-403, 72922, and Ce-64 was higher than that of Minghui-63, a widely used restorer in hybrid rice production, and the GCA of 6323 and Hui-552 was lower. Both N-Qing and N-17 showed higher GCA

for restorability than did N-Shan, a commonly used CMS line nuclear background in China (see table).

The relative importance analysis suggested that the restorer was ranked highest in restorability for CMS, followed by CMS line nuclear background, and N-R interaction. The GCA of the restorer and the nuclear background of the CMS line primarily determined the restorability for CMS (accounting for 86.4%), with specific combining ability (13.6%) having some influence.

Thus, to improve CMS restorability, emphasis must be placed on the selection of restorers and maintainers (the nuclear background of CMS lines) with higher GCA. HR195 and N-Qing have therefore been exploited in hybrid rice breeding for their higher GCA for CMS restorability. ■

Male sterile line in rice (*Oryza sativa*) developed with *O. glumaepatula* cytoplasm

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Most of the commercial hybrids of indica rice are based on the wild abortive (WA) source of cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS). More than 95% of all hybrid rice grown in China is based on the WA cytoplasmic system. Such cytoplasmic uniformity of hybrid rice could lead to genetic vulnerability to diseases and insects. To overcome this problem, diversification of the source of CMS is essential.

We developed a CMS line with the cytoplasm of AA genome wild species

O. glumaepatula and the nuclear genome of IR64. Serving as female parents, 48 accessions of 3 wild species (AA genome) were crossed with IR64, one of the restorers of

WA cytoplasm. Data on pollen sterility were recorded in F₁ and backcross generations. Hybrids showing 70% or more pollen sterility were subsequently

Pollen fertility of F₁ and backcross progenies derived from the cross of *O. glumaepatula* (Acc 100969) and IR64.

Generation	Pollen fertility (% of progeny) ^a					Plants analyzed (no.)
	CS	S	PS	PF	F	
BC ₈	100	0	0	0	0	45
BC ₇	92	8	0	0	0	12
BC ₆	86	14	0	0	0	41
BC ₅	95	4	1	0	0	147
BC ₄	57	43	0	0	0	7
BC ₃	65	20	10	5	0	20
BC ₂	0	2	16	43	39	89
BC ₁	21	23	30	14	12	197
F ₁	17	83	0	0	0	6

^aPollen fertility classes: CS = completely sterile, 0% pollen fertility; S = sterile, 1-10% pollen fertility; PS = partially sterile, 11.30% pollen fertility; PF = partially fertile, 31.60% pollen fertility; F = fertile, 61.100% pollen fertility.

A new cytoplasmic male sterile line, IR69700 A, has the cytoplasm of *O. glumaepatula* and nuclear background of IR64.

backcrossed with the recurrent parent. Of all the backcross derivatives, one line with *O. glumaepatula* (Acc 100969) cytoplasm was found to be stable for complete pollen sterility (see table). This line was designated as IR69700 A. Earlier, we developed a CMS line (IR66707 A) with *O. perennis* (Acc 104823) cytoplasm and the nuclear genome of IR64.

Crosses of IR69700A with nine restorers of WA cytoplasm show almost complete (88-100%) pollen sterility, indicating that the male sterility source of IR69700 A is different from WA cytoplasm. The new CMS line is now in BC10 and resembles maintainer IR69700 B in morphological characters, except that it flowers 5-7 d later (see figure). This line is completely sterile and does not set any seed upon selfing. We are searching for restorers of this male sterile line for use in hybrid rice breeding. ■

Pattern of segregation for grain weight involving bold and slender-grained rice varieties

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Fine-grained rice varieties are generally preferred in the market and sell for a premium price. Grain weight determines the fineness of the grain. We evaluated the pattern of segregation for grain weight in the F₂ generation for four parents: TKM 9 (short bold), IR50 (long slender), White Ponni (medium slender), and Pusa Basmati 1 (extra long slender) with contrasting grain types.

We grew 30 plants for each replication of P₁, P₂, and F₁ in two 3-m rows and 120 plants of F₂ in eight rows during 1992 dry

Pattern of segregation for hundred-grain weight in F₂ progenies.

season. The trial was replicated three times. One seedling hill⁻¹ was planted using a spacing of 30 × 30 cm. Ten plants replication⁻¹ in P₁, P₂, and F₁ and 70 plants replication⁻¹ in F₂ were evaluated for hundred-grain weight.

Among the parents, White Ponni possessed the least grain weight (0.016 g). The F₁ was intermediate between the parents in two crosses and exceeded the parental limits in IR50/Pusa Basmati 1. All crosses showed transgressive segregation for grain weight in both directions. White Ponni/Pusa Basmati 1 recorded the least mean grain weight in F₁ and F₂ generations with a high coefficient of variation (see table). It possessed high frequency (45 plants) of fine-grained segregants (0.014-0.017 g) and offers scope for selection. The cross involving bold- and slender-grained varieties (TKM9/Pusa Basmati 1) registered high frequency of progenies with grain weight of more than 0.022 g (see figure). ■

Mean performance, range, and coefficient of variation for hundred-grain weight.

Cross combination	Mean					Range (g)	CV (%)
	Pistil parent	Pollen parent	F ₁	F ₂			
TKM9/Pusa Basmati 1	2.41 + 0.01	1.88 + 0.01	2.11 + 0.02	2.13 + 0.01	1.6 - 2.8	9.44	
IR50/Pusa Basmati 1	1.80 + 0.01	1.88 + 0.01	1.98 + 0.02	1.94 + 0.01	1.6 - 2.5	8.15	
White Ponni/Pusa Basmati 1	1.67 + 0.01	1.88 + 0.01	1.79 + 0.01	1.76 + 0.01	1.4 - 2.3	10.40	